

Enhancing Financial Inclusion through Financial Literacy: Perceptions and Impact of Investment Deposits in Islamic Finance in Bosnia and Herzegovina

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to examine the awareness and perceptions of depositors in Bosnia and Herzegovina regarding the features of investment deposits in Islamic finance. It evaluates the contribution of mudarabah-based deposits to the financial inclusion of Muslims and identifies factors influencing clients' decisions to place their funds in Islamic banks. The study employs a quantitative research methodology, utilizing an online survey distributed via LimeSurvey to collect primary data. The survey targeted bank clients in Bosnia and Herzegovina, and a non-random convenience sample was obtained by promoting the survey link on a Facebook page aimed at users in the region. Paid advertising was used to enhance visibility, and direct outreach was conducted in cities with Islamic bank branches to ensure a representative sample. The survey included questions on demographic information, awareness of investment deposits, understanding of Islamic finance, and attitudes towards banking risks and returns. The structured nature of the survey allowed for effective data collection and analysis to identify knowledge gaps and depositor attitudes. The findings reveal that a significant portion of respondents lack adequate knowledge about investment deposits, posing a critical barrier to their effective use for mobilizing savings and enhancing financial inclusion. Muslim clients identify interest as a significant hurdle to saving in conventional banks, with similar expectations and risk aversion observed in Islamic banking investment accounts. This research underscores the potential role of investment deposits in advancing financial inclusion by addressing knowledge gaps and examining factors influencing clients' decision-making processes. It highlights the need for increased awareness and education about investment deposits to facilitate their wider adoption among depositors, enhancing the understanding of leveraging Islamic finance principles to promote financial inclusion and meet the unique needs of Islamic savers and investors in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Financial inclusion, an important aspect of economic development, has garnered significant attention in recent years. It entails providing individuals with access to a wide range of affordable financial services, enabling them to save, invest, and participate actively in the formal financial system (Čihák et al., 2021). In many Muslim countries, promoting financial inclusion holds immense potential for fostering socio-economic growth and reducing disparities among its diverse population (Karlan et al., 2021).

Despite the recognized potential of financial inclusion to contribute to socio-economic growth,

especially in Muslim countries, there remains a significant gap in understanding and utilizing financial products aligned with Islamic principles, such as the *Mudarabah* model in investment deposits (Ahmed & Grais, 2014). This study aims to bridge this gap by exploring the role of these Islamic financial instruments in enhancing financial inclusion among Muslims in Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H). It investigates depositors' knowledge and perceptions, and the factors influencing their decisions to engage with Islamic banks, specifically through investment deposits based on the *Mudarabah* model. The research seeks to address the barriers to financial inclusion posed by knowledge deficits, thereby contributing to broader economic development efforts in the region.

Investment deposits in Islamic finance are fundamentally different from the fixed-term deposits found in conventional banking (Cerović et al., 2017; Lee & Isa, 2019). These deposits are based on contracts grounded in Islamic finance principles, utilizing agreements such as *Qard*, *Wadiah*, and *Mudarabah* (Imady & Seibel, 2006). Specifically, Islamic banks operate on a profit-loss sharing system, where investment deposits are based on *Mudarabah* contracts, allowing customers to share in the profits and losses of the bank (Warninda, 2023).

Unlike conventional banking deposit agreements, these contracts introduce distinct differences in the nature of contractual risks, returns, or yields (Rammal, 2003).

However, there have been claims by practitioners and researchers in Islamic banking that the full implementation of investment deposit contracts is not always upheld in practice (Khan et al., 2021). Both Islamic banks' adherence to the contractual terms and depositors' perception of the possibility of realizing the risk of partial loss of principal have come under scrutiny. Depositors often expect Islamic banks to cover potential losses, despite Islamic economic principles stating that such compensation is infeasible for this deposit type. This expectation may stem from a lack of knowledge or misconceptions about Islamic banking, heavily influenced by conventional banking norms, or from the regulatory framework that affects Islamic banking's implementation in a specific country. Thus, the primary objective of this research is to investigate the level of knowledge and perception among depositors in B&H regarding the characteristics of investment deposits as outlined in Islamic finance theory. Furthermore, the study aims to explore the practical applicability of these deposit types from both a regulatory perspective and the acceptance by clients.

The results of this investigation will present essential insights for policymakers, financial institutions, and stakeholders focused on enhancing financial inclusion in B&H. They will emphasize the vital importance of investment deposits in bridging the gap between conventional and Islamic banking. This article advocates for a financial ecosystem that meets the diverse needs of the population. Supported by empirical research, this approach outlines a path toward a more inclusive financial system that could greatly aid in wider socio-economic development (Ozili, 2022).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Financial inclusion, defined as providing individuals with access to a range of affordable financial services (Dev, 2006), is a critical aspect of socio-economic development. Islamic finance operates on the principles of equity, risk-sharing, and ethical investment, providing a unique framework for financial transactions aligned with Shariah principles (Hassan & Kayed, 2009). Studies made by authors such as Shinkafi et al. (2020), Baber (2020), Siddiqui et al. (2021) have highlighted the potential of Islamic finance to enhance financial inclusion by catering to the specific needs and religious beliefs of Muslim individuals. Islamic financial instruments, such as profit-sharing agreements (*Mudarabah*), joint ventures (*Musharakah*), and Islamic microfinance, have been examined as effective tools for expanding financial access to underserved Muslim populations.

When exploring the determinants of Islamic financial inclusion in Indonesia, Ali et al. (2020)

revealed that both supply and demand factors significantly influence Islamic financial inclusion. Key demand factors identified include financial literacy, religious commitment, socioeconomic factors, and social influence. On the supply side, critical factors are human capital, product and service offerings, infrastructure, and policies and regulations. Most of the literature on the financial inclusion and Islamic finance actually revolves around these factors.

The most prominent supply factor in the literature on Islamic finance inclusion is the existence of the necessary infrastructure (Wilson, 2000; Kamer et al., 2015). More specifically, the studies have highlighted the importance of establishing Islamic banking institutions and the role of regulations and policies in facilitating their growth (Johnson, 2013). Factors such as geographical availability and proximity to Islamic banking branches have been identified as crucial determinants of access to Islamic financial services (Chowdhury & Rasid, 2016). Further, Shinkafi et al. (2020) review research on factors promoting financial inclusion in Islamic finance, highlighting key drivers for inclusion among women, low-income earners, and the rural poor. According to them, these include advanced technology, microcredit and microfinance services, legal and regulatory frameworks, and infrastructure. They conclude their study by highlighting that a broad framework integrating technology, political commitment, financial access, and awareness is vital for achieving financial inclusion in the Muslim world.

However, infrastructure alone does not guarantee increased use of Islamic banking services. Specifically, financial literacy is one of the most important drivers of financial inclusion (Smolo et al., 2022). Islamic financial literacy emerges as the most significant demand factor affecting Islamic financial inclusion. Even Shinkafi et al. (2020), who heavily emphasized the role of supply factors in promoting Islamic financial inclusion, acknowledged the importance of demand factors like public awareness of Islamic finance and Islamic financial literacy. The study by Albaity and Rahman (2019) assesses Islamic financial literacy and its impact—along with awareness, reputation, and attitudes towards Islamic banking—on the intention to use Islamic banking. Interestingly, while cost and benefit factors were not found to significantly affect intention, Islamic financial literacy, awareness, reputation, and attitude did. Initially, Islamic financial literacy showed a negative correlation with usage intention, but this turned positive when mediated by attitudes towards Islamic banking. The findings underline the critical role of enhancing Islamic financial knowledge and fostering positive attitudes towards Islamic banks to boost usage intention.

The role of Islamic financial literacy in general and Islamic financial knowledge in specific is the evident in some other studies as well. However, the customer behavior in Islamic banking is a relatively underexplored area, with one of the first studies published in 1989 by Erol and El-Bdour, focusing on “Attitudes, Behavior, and Patronage Factors of Bank Customers towards Islamic Banks.” Another early study in Malaysia by Haron et al. in 1994 echoed similar findings. These initial investigations revealed that although customers are aware of Islamic banks and their distinct products, their knowledge remains limited. This gap in understanding is identified as a primary barrier preventing wider adoption of Islamic banking services. Further research by Hamid and Nordin (2001) in Kuala Lumpur, involving both conventional and Islamic bank clients, supported these findings. More recently, Haque et al. (2009) confirmed that the situation regarding clients’ knowledge of Islamic banking products in Malaysia has seen little improvement. This consistent theme highlights the crucial need for enhanced educational efforts to bridge the knowledge gap and foster greater engagement with Islamic banking.

The importance of knowledge of Islamic banking is evident in the results of studies from other countries too. For instance, Metawa and Almosawi (1998) focused on Bahrain, Bley and Kuehn (2004) on the UAE, and Naser et al. (1999) on Jordan. Namely, these studies reveal that clients in the Middle East generally understand basic banking products like savings or current accounts and ATMs. However, they show less familiarity with complex Islamic finance models such as Mudarabah and

Musharaka, leading to less frequent use. Additionally, the studies highlight that the use of Arabic financial terminology can confuse clients. Unsurprisingly, native Arabic speakers tend to have a better grasp of Islamic banking concepts, suggesting a language barrier impacts understanding of these financial models.

Some studies revealed the importance of non-financial factors in Islamic financial inclusion. For example, in their study, Haron and Shanmugam (1995) discovered that BIMB Islamic bank depositors did not prioritize profit rates when deciding where to place their deposits. Surprisingly, they found an inverse relationship between profit rates on deposits and the levels of deposits, contradicting typical depositor behavior. A more recent investigation by Mohd Karim (2010) further examined attitudes towards Islamic deposits. These studies collectively suggest that clients choose certain Islamic banking products for religious reasons, rather than for expected profits. Additionally, a study by the State Bank of Pakistan (Durrani, 2016) showed that 62 percent of surveyed individuals were willing to pay more for Sharia-compliant banking products. Meanwhile, 36 percent stated they would not withdraw their investment if the bank reported negative returns, highlighting the significance of Sharia compliance over financial returns among Pakistani banking clients.

Similarly, article by Karlan et al. (2021) studies the preference for Sharia-compliant loans over conventional loans in a Muslim-majority country, finding a stronger demand and a higher willingness to pay for sharia-compliant products despite their financial similarities to conventional options. The study reveals that the authorizing entity has little effect on the demand for these loans, but price sensitivity varies with religiosity, as shown by viewership of religious TV. It suggests that survey data may overstate the exclusionary influence of religious goals, underlining the role of religious and social factors in credit decisions. The findings highlight the potential for financial inclusion by acknowledging non-financial preferences in financial decision-making. Products designed to meet these preferences, even at a higher cost, can attract individuals valuing these features, thus expanding access to formal financial services for those who might avoid them for social or religious reasons. This approach can make it economically viable to offer such products and integrate more people into the formal financial system.

The literature has identified various challenges and opportunities in the realm of financial inclusion through Islamic finance. Challenges encompass limited access to Islamic financial services, the absence of standardized Shariah-compliant products, and inadequate regulatory frameworks (Čihák & Hesse, 2010). Cultural and social factors, gender disparities, and technological barriers also pose significant impediments to financial inclusion (Warde, 2010; Kammer et al., 2015). Conversely, opportunities exist in utilizing technology for digital Islamic finance solutions, enhancing partnerships between Islamic financial institutions and conventional banks, and promoting financial education and awareness (Dusuki & Abdullah, 2007; Iqbal & Molyneux, 2016).

3. POSSIBILITIES OF INVESTMENT ACCOUNTS IMPLEMENTATION IN CONVENTIONAL REGULATORY ENVIRONMENT IN EUROPE

Implementing investment deposit models in B&H can be explored and achieved through several approaches, which include regulatory framework, awareness and education, technology, and partnerships.

For successful implementation of investment deposits, regulatory bodies should consider adapting regulations and creating an appropriate framework that supports this type of banking product. This includes establishing rules for the formation and management of investment deposits, as well as ensuring the protection of investor interests. Banking institutions can invest efforts in educating clients about investment deposits and their benefits. This may involve organizing seminars,

workshops, and campaigns to enhance awareness about the potential advantages and risks associated with such products.

Banks can establish partnerships with investment institutions to leverage their knowledge and expertise in investment management. This can enable access to a wide range of investment opportunities and portfolio diversification for investment deposits. Banking institutions can leverage advanced technologies such as digital platforms and process automation to facilitate the opening and management of investment deposits. This can improve the user experience and provide faster and more efficient services to investors. Collaborating with international institutions such as international banks or investment funds can provide additional support and knowledge regarding the implementation of investment deposits. These partnerships can open new opportunities for investors and grant access to global markets.

Deposit insurance is the first characteristic of the domestic banking system that we will analyze in the context of investment deposit based on Mudarabah. According to Article 14 of the Law on Banks of the Federation of B&H (2017), „All banks to which the Agency has granted a banking license shall be obliged to fulfill the membership conditions for deposit insurance in order to retain their license.“ Furthermore, Article 17 of the same law states that a bank will lose its operating license in case of non-compliance with the membership conditions in the deposit insurance system. It is clear, therefore, that investment deposits must be insured, which is not in line with the principle of Mudarabah, where the investment risk is assumed by the capital owner. This regulatory barrier can be partially overcome by informing the client that, according to Shariah, they are not allowed to withdraw the entire deposit amount in case of lower returns or losses. This is the stance of the Shariah Board of BBI Bank.

One of the major regulatory barriers for implementing deposit contracts based on Mudarabah is the Decision on the Uniform Method of Calculation and Disclosure of the Effective Interest Rate on Loans and Deposits, issued by the Federal Banking Agency in May 2012. This decision prescribes a unified method of calculation and disclosure of the effective interest rate on loans provided by banks and microcredit organizations, as well as the effective interest rate on deposits held with banks. According to this decision, the bank must inform clients of the effective interest rate before accepting a deposit request and before concluding a deposit agreement. When entering into a deposit agreement, the bank must provide the client with a copy of the repayment plan, clearly indicating the effective interest rate, which is considered an integral part of the agreement. If the effective interest rate changes due to changes in the calculation elements, the bank is required to notify the client in writing of such changes before the revised effective interest rate takes effect. In the case of variable interest rates, the bank must clearly define the conditions for changing the rate in the agreement.

Furthermore, the Law on the Protection of Financial Services Users (2014) stipulates in Article 21 that a deposit agreement must include, among other things:

4) the amount of the nominal annual interest rate, with an indication of whether the user is obliged to pay taxes;

the effective interest rate and the total amount to be paid to the user, calculated on the day of concluding the agreement;

the amount of the insured monetary deposit.

Regarding variable rates, only officially published elements such as the reference interest rate or the consumer price index can be considered variable elements. The return on a specific investment pool cannot be considered an officially published element, and therefore, it cannot determine the

return on deposits with variable rates. Moreover, even if it were possible, the law states that the bank must inform the user in written or electronic form about any changes in the rate before the revised rate takes effect. With investment deposits, it is not possible to apply any predetermined rate of return; the return is determined subsequently.

Similar legal solutions are prescribed in the Law on Banks of the Republika Srpska in Article 98, which requires that the deposit agreement indicate the nominal and effective interest rates, as well as the total amount to be paid to the user upon maturity.

Based on all the aforementioned, we can conclude that the first hypothesis, which states, “It is possible to apply deposit contracts based on profit sharing from investment in B&H,” is rejected. Due to certain provisions of the laws of the Government of the Federation of B&H and the sublegal acts of the Banking Agency of the Federation of B&H, which primarily aim to protect clients, it is not possible to implement deposit contracts based on profit sharing from investment of deposit funds.

These legal barriers and regulations pose significant challenges to the implementation of investment deposit models based on Mudarabah in B&H. They require deposit insurance, standardized calculation and disclosure of interest rates, and specific provisions in deposit agreements that may not align with the principles of Mudarabah. As a result, the application of such deposit contracts is currently not feasible within the existing legal framework.

It is important to note that these regulatory barriers can be overcome through amendments to the relevant laws and regulations or the introduction of specific provisions that accommodate the principles of Mudarabah and enable the implementation of investment deposit models in accordance with Islamic finance principles. However, such changes would require a comprehensive review and adjustment of the legal framework governing banking and financial services in B&H.

Therefore, while the potential for implementing investment deposit models based on Mudarabah exists in theory, the current regulatory landscape in B&H presents significant challenges and limitations. Any future progress in this regard would require a comprehensive and coordinated effort involving regulatory authorities, Islamic financial institutions, and relevant stakeholders to create a conducive legal and regulatory environment for the implementation of investment deposit contracts based on profit sharing.

Furthermore, there are several open questions that need to be addressed before the implementation of this type of deposit. Some of the areas to consider include:

- Defining the accounting treatment for recording each individual fund (which accounts to use for these funds, how to record the return of principal and profit)
- Defining the accounting treatment for reserves (PER and IRR)
- Defining the accounting treatment for recording gross profit
- Defining the accounting treatment for direct costs related to mudaraba investments (costs deducted from gross profit)
- Defining the accounting treatment or accounts for recording allocated or net profit (profit sharing between the client and the bank)
- Defining the accounting treatment for realized losses from a project and how to record them based on individual client investments
- Defining the accounting treatment for placements from sources based on mudaraba
- Defining the accounting treatment for returns from such placements (principal

and profit)

- Defining the accounting treatment for provisions related to these placements (provision costs should belong to mudaraba investors according to the mudaraba model)
- Defining the accounting treatment in case a placement becomes non-performing (this cost should be passed on to the investors according to the mudaraba agreement)
- Defining the accounting treatment in case of collecting disputed receivables (these receivables should also belong to the investors)

In addition to the accounting treatment, it is necessary to define how PER and IRR reserves could function, the stance of the Federal Banking Agency on the fact that the expected return is not guaranteed in these deposits, as well as the procedure in case of loss and the procedure in case the bank collects the return subsequently (e.g., through legal action). Managing various types of risks, both “conventional” and specific to this type of product, is also an open question.

Regarding future research, Article 39 of the Law on Banks of the Federation of B&H specifies the activities that a bank can carry out in the territory of the Federation of B&H. Among other things, a bank can accept all types of monetary deposits and engage in financial management services. An issue for future research is whether a bank’s activities with investment accounts can be categorized as financial management rather than deposit-taking activities. The role of the bank in investment accounts is closer to financial management than deposit-taking activities.

In this chapter, we have examined the possibilities of implementing investment accounts in the practice of Islamic banks in B&H, taking into account the legal regulations and other conditions. In the next chapter, we will explore the market for such products, specifically the perspective of potential depositors.

4. EXAMINING CLIENT PERCEPTION

A significant number of both published and unpublished (intended only for internal use) research studies focus on conventional banking, with a considerable portion analyzing clients’ motives for selecting a banking service provider. This study blends exploratory and descriptive research approaches. In the exploratory phase, we aim to explore depositors’ perceptions of the unique characteristics of investment deposit accounts. Descriptively, this study aims to enrich the existing literature in the field.

4.1. Methodology

In this research, we employ a quantitative approach using survey methods to test auxiliary hypotheses. The questionnaire was distributed via LimeSurvey, an online platform. We analyzed primary data collected from the survey to understand Islamic bank clients’ perceptions of investment deposit accounts and their features. Primary data is deemed ideal for this type of research as it provides direct insights from the target population (Groves et al., 2009). The hypotheses tested in this study include:

- The majority of bank clients in B&H are not sufficiently familiar with the concept of investment deposits in Islamic banking.
- The majority of bank clients in B&H expect the bank to provide the same returns regardless of the bank’s business performance.
- The majority of bank clients in B&H are willing to accept higher risk in investment deposits in exchange for the potential of higher returns compared to the existing returns

achievable with fixed deposits.

The structured nature of surveys allows for direct data collection from a broad audience, aligning with our exploratory and descriptive objectives to identify knowledge gaps and depositor attitudes effectively (Fowler, 2014). The survey was designed to directly align with our research objectives, consisting of structured questions across several sections. Initially, it gathers demographic information to segment analysis by relevant variables (age, income, banking history). Following sections delve into respondents' awareness of investment deposits, understanding of Islamic finance, and attitudes towards banking risks and returns. Questions mix multiple-choice for straightforward topics and Likert scales for nuanced issues, crafted to be clear and accessible to those unfamiliar with banking terminologies (Likert, 1932).

The survey consists of six main questions, two of which have additional sub-questions. The questions are divided into two groups. The first group of questions explores socio-demographic information about the respondents, as well as their knowledge level regarding investment deposits. The second group of questions analyzes the respondents' attitudes towards the unique characteristics of investment accounts. All questions are closed-ended with multiple-choice options, while the last two questions are created in the form of a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 (being strongly disagree and strongly agree). According to DeVellis (2016) such question format is preferable both in terms of response rate, as they are easier to answer, and in terms of analyzing the obtained responses.

4.2. Sample

In this research, the target population comprises bank clients in B&H. A bank client is defined as any individual who holds an account with any bank, regardless of the type of account. Due to the unfeasibility of surveying the entire population, a non-random convenience sample was selected as a representative subset. The sample was obtained by strategically promoting the survey link, along with accompanying messages, on a Facebook page specifically targeted at users in B&H. Paid advertising on Facebook was utilized to increase the visibility of the survey among the target audience.

Facebook was selected for sample recruitment due to its wide reach and advanced targeting features, allowing us to engage a diverse demographic likely to have banking experience. Targeting was based on location, age, and interests related to finance and banking. To mitigate potential online sampling biases (e.g., over-representation of tech-savvy individuals), we also targeted specific regions with Islamic bank branches and conducted direct outreach to ensure a broader sample.

To ensure the inclusion of an adequate number of respondents who are clients of Islamic banks, additional efforts were made. Specifically, cities where BBI Bank operates its branches were targeted to capture a representative sample of Islamic banking clients. Furthermore, direct outreach was conducted to individuals who were assumed to be potential users of Islamic banking services, thereby diversifying the sample.

Considering the nature of a non-probabilistic sample, the determination of the sample size took into account both practical considerations and the cost-benefit ratio. The aim was to strike a balance between obtaining a sufficient number of responses and optimizing available resources.

Ultimately, a total of 444 respondents engaged in the process of completing the survey. The overall sample size can be considered adequate for the purposes of analysis and drawing meaningful conclusions.

4.3. Results and analysis

In the analysis of the survey results, we will focus on the responses provided by the participants, particularly on several questions that test specific hypotheses. Regarding the composition of the respondents, 23% of them are clients of Islamic bank, while two-thirds are clients of other banks, with 8.8% of the respondents not providing a response to this question. The majority of respondents (53.16%) have only a current account, while 15.79% have a savings account, and 5.79% have a fixed-term deposit account at a bank. The largest proportion of respondents (39%) have monthly incomes below 1,000 KM, and the percentage of respondents decreases with increasing income levels.

Regarding the first hypothesis tested, the survey results indicate that the majority of respondents indeed have insufficient knowledge about investment deposits, thereby confirming the hypothesis. Additional questions further support the finding of a general lack of awareness regarding investment deposits. This outcome is anticipated, given the limited availability of this product in B&H and the lack of active education efforts by the local Islamic bank on investment deposits. Nonetheless, Islamic bank clients showed significantly greater knowledge of this product than those of conventional banks. This suggests that Islamic bank clients likely gained familiarity with investment deposits through their education, information from friends or bank staff, or the printed materials distributed by BBI Bank to promote Islamic banking.

The next hypothesis, which explores whether clients would be willing to accept higher risk in investment deposits for the potential of higher returns, is partially confirmed. It is important to note that the median response is “Partially agree,” not “Completely agree.” This indicates that while clients are open to a higher risk level, there is a limit to this willingness. Additionally, Islamic bank clients show a greater readiness to embrace this risk, likely due to the perception that investment deposits align better with the Islamic economy compared to other deposit types. However, the majority of respondents believe that the Islamic bank should absorb any losses that occur. Differences emerge between clients of Islamic and conventional banks: those from conventional banks tend to believe the bank should bear the loss, whereas Islamic bank clients, more cognizant of Sharia principles in the *mudarabah* contract, show a greater willingness to accept the loss themselves.

The majority of respondents expressed a desire to diversify their savings by allocating some of their funds to investment deposits. However, over two-thirds expect the bank to avoid excessively risky investments with the funds from these deposits. Therefore, whether this hypothesis is definitively confirmed depends on the specific level of risk and the expected returns achievable.

Regarding the hypothesis related to the expectation of constant returns, most clients still prioritize consistent returns on their deposits, independent of the bank’s investment performance. The data shows that a significant number of clients prefer predictable rates of return on their investments. Yet, a considerable group of respondents does not align with this perspective, showing openness to variable returns based on different situations. This is underscored by responses to whether clients would accept the bank setting aside profits to cover future losses, with the majority in favor, supporting the hypothesis of constant and predictable returns. Further evidence for this hypothesis comes from inquiries about withdrawal behaviors in response to lower-than-expected returns. Over half of the clients (52%) indicated they would withdraw their deposits under such circumstances, whereas 37% would not. Additionally, in scenarios of realized Sharia risk, over 70% of respondents would withdraw their deposits. About 65% of respondents would hesitate to deposit if the principal amount lacked deposit insurance. Moreover, nearly all clients expressed a desire for transparency regarding the utilization of investment deposit funds and requested detailed explanations of the Sharia aspects of the investment deposit agreement from bank representatives.

In summary, the survey results offer valuable insights into respondents’ awareness and preferences

concerning investment deposits. The data reveal a general lack of knowledge and understanding of this financial product among most participants. Nonetheless, Islamic bank clients demonstrate a greater familiarity with investment deposits, likely attributed to prior exposure through educational efforts or bank interactions. Attitudes towards accepting higher risks for the potential of higher returns also differ, with Islamic bank clients displaying a greater openness to risk. Furthermore, while a significant number of clients show a preference for stable and predictable returns, opinions on this matter vary. The findings illuminate the perceptions and expectations clients hold towards investment deposits, presenting essential information for Islamic and conventional banks in B&H.

5. IMPLICATIONS

The results of this study on depositor perceptions and knowledge regarding Islamic banking investment deposits in B&H have important implications for policymakers, financial institutions, and stakeholders focused on improving financial inclusion. By uncovering depositor attitudes towards Islamic banking, especially investment deposits, the study highlights a significant knowledge gap. Addressing this gap could markedly influence the landscape of financial inclusion.

For policymakers, the study emphasizes the need to create regulatory frameworks and educational initiatives tailored to the distinct features of Islamic banking. Enhancing public comprehension of Islamic finance principles can demystify investment deposits, promoting broader engagement with the banking system.

Financial institutions, particularly those providing Islamic banking services, can utilize these findings to refine their product offerings and marketing approaches, aligning more closely with the needs and expectations of prospective depositors. This entails developing clearer and more accessible informational resources that elucidate the principles and advantages of investment deposits, thereby bridging the knowledge gap highlighted in the study.

The study underscores the potential appeal of Islamic banking to depositors seeking alternatives to conventional banking, motivated by religious or ethical considerations. Financial institutions could develop innovative products that resonate with these preferences, ensuring competitive returns and security. This approach addresses the financial and ethical considerations of potential clients.

Additionally, the findings indicate a willingness among certain population segments to embrace the higher risks of investment deposits for the chance of higher returns. This reveals a market opportunity for Islamic banks to create and offer investment products that accommodate different risk tolerances, all while staying true to principles of Islamic finance.

6. CONCLUSION

This research on the role of investment deposits in Islamic banking and their potential to boost financial inclusion in B&H reveals several key insights. Investment deposits, based on the mudarabah principle, offer a unique avenue for individuals with excess funds to participate in profit-sharing endeavors with Islamic banks. In this arrangement, the bank acts as the mudarib (manager), and the depositor provides capital, forming a partnership where both returns and risks are shared, without guarantees on the principal or returns.

Our analysis of the adoption and perception of these deposits in B&H has produced complex results. Contrary to the hypothesis that the profit-sharing model of Islamic banking would fit easily into the B&H financial environment, we encountered significant legal and regulatory barriers. The requirement for banks to provide fixed return rates upfront clashes with the inherent uncertainty of mudarabah contracts, highlighting a critical mismatch. This conflict indicates the need for

regulatory reform, perhaps looking towards models like the ones in Malaysia. There, investment accounts are differentiated from standard deposit contracts, more closely resembling financial management practices than traditional deposit-taking, suggesting a pathway for integration into B&H's financial system.

Survey responses from 444 bank clients in B&H further illuminate the current state of awareness and attitudes towards Islamic banking's investment deposits:

- i. A substantial segment of the population is unfamiliar with investment deposits, likely attributed to the absence of these products in the local market. This gap highlights the urgent need for educational efforts to bridge the knowledge divide.
- ii. There is a prevalent expectation among respondents for stable returns from banking investments, mirroring practices in other regions where Islamic banks maintain reserves to stabilize depositor returns. This finding highlights a fundamental tension between the expectations of depositors and the risk-sharing principles of Islamic finance.
- iii. Despite this, there is a noticeable willingness among respondents to accept higher risks for potentially greater returns, suggesting a nuanced comprehension and acceptance of the risk-reward balance inherent in *mudarabah* contracts. Yet, this acceptance is moderated by a desire for a certain level of return predictability.
- iv. The variation in responses between clients of Islamic banks and those of conventional banks illustrates the diversity in financial landscapes and depositor expectations within B&H. These insights challenge traditional views on the compatibility of Islamic banking with the B&H financial system and shed light on both the opportunities and obstacles for its deeper integration and acceptance.

This study establishes a foundation for a wider dialogue on the contribution of Islamic finance to financial inclusion. It urges a collaborative approach among policymakers, regulators, and Islamic financial institutions to overcome legal hurdles, improve public comprehension of Islamic finance principles, and develop financial products that align with depositor expectations under Islamic banking principles. Future research should explore the socio-economic implications of incorporating Islamic finance more fully into B&H and Herzegovina's financial system, examining the potential benefits and challenges that accompany such integration.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study provides important insights into depositor perceptions and knowledge regarding Islamic banking's investment deposits in B&H. However, it faces several limitations that highlight areas for future research. The use of an online survey distributed via Facebook may not fully represent the broader population's views, particularly those less engaged with digital platforms. The reliance on self-reported data risks social desirability bias, potentially skewing the accuracy of depositor behaviors and perceptions. Additionally, the study's cross-sectional design captures attitudes at a specific point in time without accounting for dynamic changes in the financial landscape or depositor perspectives.

Future research could benefit from a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative interviews or focus groups to delve deeper into the motivations behind depositor attitudes towards Islamic banking. Longitudinal studies would offer valuable insights into how these attitudes evolve over time in response to changing market conditions and regulatory environments. Expanding the geographic scope of the research and targeting non-users of banking services would enhance understanding of the factors influencing the adoption of Islamic banking products. Moreover, assessing the impact of Islamic banking on depositor financial health and community economic development

could provide concrete evidence of its benefits and limitations for financial inclusion.

Declarations

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The data are available upon a reasonable request from the corresponding author.

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